

VI International Forum on Teacher Education

Zero Exponents in the Russian Language and Peculiarities of Their Learning

Tatyana A. Korneyeva* (a)

(a) *Kazan Federal University, 420008, Kazan (Russia), 18 Kremlyovskaya street,
tatyana.tak1110@gmail.com*

Abstract

The research aims at finding methods and techniques for intensifying educational activities of students in the study of the Russian language, increasing their motivation, developing creative potential, and meaningfully studying the facts of the Russian language using the capabilities of the digital educational environment.

The purpose of the article is to justify the effectiveness of accessing digital resources, primarily the National Corpus of the Russian Language as an information and reference system based on a collection of Russian texts in electronic form, providing wide access to linguistic and speech facts in the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language.

Research objectives: to analyze the features of the methodology for studying word formation using data from the National Corpus of the Russian Language (NCRL) and to show the possibilities of using the corpus to identify semantic differences between word-building synonyms.

The main research methods include theoretical analysis of scientific and educational literature, language analysis method, pedagogical observation, modeling of the educational process, conversation method.

Key findings of the study are 1) we considered the productive word-formation types of zero suffix names in scientific grammar and educational-methodical complexes, 2) we analyzed NCRL materials on the derivational synonymy of names of zero suffixation and semantic with a variety of synonyms, 3) we have proven the need to use digital educational resources in the educational process and, above all, the opportunities provided for the Russian language project by the NCRL project.

Keywords: Russian language, zero exponents, zero suffixation, zero morpheme, digitalization of education.

© 2020 Tatyana A. Korneyeva

This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published by Kazan federal university and peer-reviewed under responsibility of IFTE-2020 (VI International Forum on Teacher Education)

*Corresponding author. E-mail: tatyana.tak1110@gmail.com

Introduction

The process of development of digital pedagogy in Russia, the widespread use of information and communication technologies in the educational process, active application of electronic library resources and systems for automatically translating texts and speech from various languages in the educational environment, in general, digitalization of education require the formation of students' ability to work with information (information competencies) and developing learning reading skills. In the practice of teaching Russian as a native or a foreign language, the requirement for learning reading skills is necessary when analyzing linguistic material and comparing linguistic units that are similar in meaning and are represented in different linguistic bodies.

The research problem consists at finding methods and techniques for intensifying the educational activities of students in the study of the Russian language, increasing their motivation, developing creative potential, and meaningfully studying the facts of the Russian language using the capabilities of the digital educational environment.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to justify the effectiveness of accessing digital resources, primarily the National Corps of the Russian Language as an information and reference system based on a collection of Russian texts in electronic form, providing wide access to linguistic and speech facts in the process of teaching Russian as a native or a foreign language.

Literature review

The phenomenon of zero suffixation is described in detail in fundamental scientific works by Markov (2001), Lopatin (1966), Zemskaya (2013), Nikolaev (2010, 2011), Shansky (1968), and other scientists. The phenomenon of zero suffixation is one of the debatable issues of linguistics (Korneyeva 2016, 2019; Shaikhutdinova, Korneyeva, & Markova, 2016, 2017; Volskaya, Korneyeva, & Markova, 2018). The contradictions in science cause inaccuracies in the compilation of didactic materials for teaching at school and university.

Methodology

The main research methods include: theoretical analysis of scientific and educational literature, methods of language analysis, pedagogical observation, modeling of the educational process, conversation method. The study of special literature on the topic made it possible to identify the main methods and techniques used in

teaching Russian as a native or a foreign language, to focus on the use of information technologies in the educational process, to identify language difficulties that students encounter at the initial and advanced stages of training. Modeling of the educational process made it possible to single out learning strategies and tactics, predict student behavior, and optimally organize the educational process. Pedagogical observation made it possible to collect factual material and analyze the learning outcomes. Using the method of language analysis, language facts are revealed that require didactic support and implementation in educational activities, an idea is formed about further improvement of the educational process. The method of conversation helped to identify psychological characteristics of students in the study of material of increased complexity and the impact on them of the proposed learning system.

Results

The names of zero suffixation in the Russian language are verbal, adjective, substantive formations, united by a common structural feature, namely the presence of a materially not expressed word-forming morpheme, which in some cases is revealed in the word-formation paradigm (as, for example, in the cases: *begat'* – *beganiye*, *begotnya*, *beg*; *khodit'* – *khozhdeniye*, *khod*; *siniy* – *sineva*, *sin'* etc.). In grammatical terms, these are the nouns of the masculine, middle gender of the first declension (*vkhod*, *delo*), the feminine and general gender of the second declension (*igra*, *podliza*), the feminine gender of the third declension (*dal'*), the nouns of the adjective declension (*Ivanova*, *dezhurnaya*) and the group pluralia tantum (*sumerki*, *vesy*); adjectives (*pyatyy*, *priyemnyy*); status category word (*zhal'*). In addition, the zero suffix element is represented in confix formations (*beskhvostyy*, *bezrogiy*), in complex nouns (*truboprovod*, *vodosbros*) and complex adjectives (*belozubyy*, *mnogogolosyy*), in adverbs (*vzamen*, *naugad*). The most productive type of formations of zero suffixation (according to the academic "Russian Grammar" (2005) includes the type of masculine nouns of the first declension with the meaning of an abstract action (state) (*khod*, *razgovor*, *oplata*, *pogonya*), word-formation types of masculine and feminine nouns with the values of a single act (*potseluy*, *vzglyad*), person - producer of the action (*storozh*, *prisluga*), tool (*nasos*, *klyuv*, *oprava*, *pila*), place of action (*vkhod*, *sklad*), item action (*dar*, *provod*, *obuv'*), of abstract feature (*zelen'*, *gorech'*) and some others. These word-building types of zero suffixation are most represented in the educational complexes of teaching Russian as a foreign language at an advanced stage of learning (level B1) (Antonova, Nakhabina, & Tolstykh, 2016, 2017; Egorova, 2016). These word-building types are paid special attention to when studying the courses "Modern Russian Language: Word Formation" and "Modern Russian Language: Morphology" as part of an advanced stage of training.

The main method of studying and introducing into speech practice formations of zero suffixation is the exercise method. The most common methods and exercises include tasks for 1) forming verbal nouns and

making phrases with them, 2) finding the root in a group of cognate words (for example, *torgovat'*, *torgovlya*, *torgovets*, *torgovyy*; *bolet'*, *bol'noy*, *bolezn'*, *bol'*), 3) to find the verbs from which the proposed nouns are formed (for example, *vkhod*, *vykhod*, *ot"yezd*, *priyezd*, *perekhod*, *pereyezd*, *polot*, *vylet*), 4) to continue a number of phrases (for example, *vkhod v metro*, *vykhod na ulitsu*, *dobycha nefti i gaza*) or 5) per expression of all possible phrases according to the model (for example, from the verbs *vypuskat'* (*gazetu*), *vybirat'* (*prezidenta*), *dobyvat'*), 6) to make sentences for this beginning (for example: *Cherez mesyats posle vstrechi...*; *Za den' do ot"yezda...*; *Za chas do otkhoda poyezda...*; *Pered snom...*), 7) for a synonymous replacement of the structure with prepositions (for example, *Pri perevode stat'i vy mozhete pol'zovat'sya slovarom*; *Pri vstreche lyudi zdorovayutsya*; *Pri vkhode v teatr zriteli pred'yavlyayut bilety kontroloru*) and other exercises. As a rule, exercises on recognition, education and introduction of speech examples of the word-formation field of verbal nouns do not contain an indication of the structural features of these words and include cases with a variety of morphemes producing, which often makes it difficult for foreign students to comprehend the peculiarities of Russian word production and leads to speech errors. Expanding the possibilities of forming sets of various exercises for studying names of zero suffixation and organizing classroom and independent work with digital educational resources using NCRL data.

First of all, the Russian National Corpus contains materials on the word-building synonymy of zero suffix names and the semantic difference of synonyms in certain contexts. If the lexical meaning of such synonyms can be clarified in explanatory dictionaries (for example, “The Great Universal Dictionary of the Russian Language” edited by Professor Morkovkin (Morkovkin, Bogacheva, & Lutsкая, 2016), then examples of use and the possibility of compatibility for the development of exercises for distinguishing semantics in NCRL are represented much more widely. For example, the word “*khod*”, which is widespread in modern Russian, has synonymous diverbates *khod'ba* and *khozhdeniye*. The main meanings of this word include: 1) moving, moving someone (*uskorit' khod*), 2) the way the athlete moves (*kon'kovyy khod lyzhnika*), 3) moving the vehicles (*dat' zadniy khod*), 4) moving any object (*nablyudat' za khodom svetil*) (Morkovkin et al., 2016). In addition, the dictionary presents isolated examples of the use of stable combinations with the word: *khod*, *byt' v khodu*, *na vsom khodu*, *na khodu*, *dat' khod (chemu-libo)*, *znat' vse khody i vykhody*, *pribavit' khodu*, *poyti v khod*, *po khodu chego-libo*, *pustit' v khod*, *protiv khoda chego-libo*, *po khodu dela*. These examples can be supplemented and contextually designed for didactic purposes by the NCRL (National corpus of the Russian language) data (for example, cases with a pretext *v khode*: *v khode raboty programmy*, *v khode rossiysko-yegipetskiikh peregovorov*, *v khode obsuzhdeniya*). The main features of the compatibility of the word *khod* include the features of coordination: *privychnyy*, *bystryy*, *medlennyy*; unprepositional grammar management: *khod sobytiy*, *spora*, *issledovaniya*, *vyborov*, *stroitel'stva*, *boya*, *razvitiya*, *peregovorov*, *rassuzhdeniy*, *istorii*; prepositional grammar management: *nablyudeniye za khodom chego-libo*, *vnimaniye k khodu chego-libo*, *vliyaniye na khod chego-libo*,

informatsiya o khode chego-libo, vmeshat'sya v khod chego-libo, sledit' za khodom chego-libo, sudit' po khodu chego-libo, etc. An analysis of the NCRF data allows us to note the predominant use of this token in the texts of scientific and journalistic styles.

The word *khod'ba* has two meanings: 1) walking (*bystraya khod'ba, ustat' ot khod'by*), 2) sport (*sportivnaya khod'ba*) (Morkovkin, Bogacheva, & Lutsкая, 2016). In a stable combination, a measure of distance is emphasized (*Universitet nakhoditsya v pyati minutakh khod'by ot doma*). Frequency expressions are presented in NCRL, for example: *khod'ba na 50 kilometrov, monotonnaya khod'ba, khod'ba v tverday i myagkoy obuvi, khod'ba po gruntu, khod'ba po domam, khod'ba v bystrom tempe, khod'ba po azimutu, khod'ba po lestnitsam, khod'ba na lyzhakh*, etc.) In the examples of NCRF, the word walking is often associated with the formation of zero suffixation *beg* (*biomekhanika cheloveka v raznykh svoikh proyavleniyakh* (*beg, khod'ba*, etc.) or other suffix formations with the meaning of abstract action (*dzhogging* (*beg trustsoy*), *plavaniye*).

The word *khozhdeniye* has four meanings: 1) action according to the meaning of the verb *khodit'*, 2) circulation of money, securities, 3) out of date. wandering, travel, 4) out of date. courtship of someone (Efremova, 2000). The first meaning in NCRL is very often found in combination of *khozhdeniye po mukam*, referring to A.N. Tolstoy (*no «Khozheniye po mukam» (ya roman chitala v 9-m klasse) kak-to ochen' sil'no poshatnul moyu veru v spravedlivost' revolyutsii; bor'ba za pravo sobstvennosti na nego bol'she pokhodit na "khozheniye po mukam", tak zachem eto khozheniye po mukam?*, or by analogy with the phrase *khozheniye v narod* (*khozheniye naroda v intelligentsiyu, "khozheniye v khippi"*), or in an ironic context (*khozheniye po chinovnikam, khozheniye po kontoram*). Less common are phrases such as *khozheniye peshkom, khozheniye bosikom, bessmyslennoye khozheniye, khozheniye za podsolnechnym maslom*. The phrase “*shirokoye khozheniye*” is used in the meaning of “distribution” (*Na protyazhenii pochty dvukh vekov v Moskve ne vstrechayutsya bukivtsy, sostavlennyye iz chelovecheskikh figur. S logkoy ruki novgorodskikh izografov oni kogda-to imeli shirokoye khozheniye v rukopisnykh knigakh Srednevekovoy Rusi...*). There are phrases with religious semantics (*khozheniye v Mekku, khozheniye po vode*), phrases referring to walking as a genre of Old Russian writing (“*Khozheniye za tri moray*” Afanasiya Nikitina, a takzhe: *velikoye khozheniye Krolika, Vinni-Pukha i Pyatachka v poiskakh sobstvennogo doma*). On the whole, the word walking in the described synonymic series *khod — khod'ba — khozheniye* in the texts of the NCRL has more pronounced national-cultural semantics and requires the use of additional background materials of linguistic and cultural orientation.

Sometimes foreign students mention a similar sounding word *khadz*. However, this word is borrowed from the Arabic language and means “a pilgrimage to Mecca to the Muslim shrine of Kaaba or to Medina

to the tomb of Muhammad, considered among Muslims a feat of piety” (Efremova, 2000). In NCRL, phrases are fixed: *sovershit' khadzh, otpravlyayutsya v khadzh, na puti v khadzh, ne imeyet deneg na khadzh, yezhegodnyy khadzh v Mekku, mesyats khadzha, net ogranicheniy dlya poyezdok v khadzh*.

Consider another pair of diverbatives: *povorachivaniye* and *povorot*. In this case, as in the previous one, the formation of zero suffixation in the semantic plane is more saturated. The main meanings of the word *povorachivaniye* include: 1) the process of changing the position of something due to the rotational movement of the hand, 2) the process of changing the position of any part of the body by turning it in a certain direction, 3) changing the direction of movement of someone or something (Morkovkin, Bogacheva, & Lutsкая, 2016). The word is formed from a verb of an imperfect form *povorachivat'*, therefore dictionary entries provide a reference to a verb of a perfect form *povernut'*, which makes it difficult for foreign students to work with lexicographic sources. When studying a derivative of a noun, it is advisable to first draw the attention of students to the peculiarities of the compatibility of the producing verb. In the NCRL, quite simple cases of its usage are recorded, and it is not difficult for foreign students to write examples of frequency expressions: *povorachivayet yego vverkh nogami, povorachivat' na 90°, povorachivayet i plyvot k lodke, povorachival golovu, povorachivat' obratno, povorachivaya napravo ili nalevo, povorachivala za ugol, povorachivayet ruchku do otkaza, povorachivayu klyuch*, as well as phrases in the figurative meaning: *solntse "povorachivayet na zimu", povorachivayete vopros v druguyu ploskost'*. A derivative noun is mainly found in texts of special literature: *zadacha, trebuyushchaya myslennogo povorachivaniya figury, rychag dlya povorachivaniya dvukh sobrannykh plit na 90 gradusov, povorachivaniye magnitnykh strelok, dlya povorachivaniya sudov, povorachivaniye golovy v odnu storonu, povorachivaniya koleasa*, etc.

The formation of zero suffixation *povorot* is a more capacious. Dictionaries indicate the following meanings of a given word: 1) a complete or partial change of someone, something by a rotational movement, as well as the action and state according to the meaning of verbs *povernut'sya, povorachivat'sya* and *povortyvatsya*; 2) a change in position (head, body) to the opposite or other; 3) a change in the direction of its movement; 4) a place where something (road, street, river) turns, deviates to the side; 5) giving something else direction. The semantics of the noun reflect not only the process, but also the result of the action. It is no coincidence that stable combinations are present only in this pairing pair: *ot vorot povorot, vpisat'sya v povorot, oboyti na povorote*, etc. The most frequent definitions of the word turn (according to NCRL) include: *strategicheskoy, syuzhetnyy, interesnyy, rezkiy*, the most frequency phrases with uncomplicated and prepositional controls should include: *povorot golovy; povorot na 60 i 120 gradusov ot gorizontali; pri povorote, pri vyyezde s peresecheniya proyeyzhey chasti; povorot sud'by* and some others.

A similar work using NCRL data can be done with synonyms: *lov-lovlya*, *sud-suzhdeniye*, *klov-klevaniye*, *rozysk-razyskivaniye*, *vizg-vizzhaniye*, *podzhog-podzhiganiye*, *beg-begotnya-begstvo*, *pusk-puskaniye*, *vzdokh-vzdykhaniye*, *kontrol'-kontrolirovaniye* and many others. As noted by Markov (2001), “the formations of zero suffixation give many examples of suffixial synonymy in parallel with the names *-ka*, *-niye*, *-stvo*, etc. One of the consequences of the interaction of names like *hod* with literary formations with the suffix *-niye* was their specialization in modern Russian early values, the ever-increasing consolidation of formations of zero suffixation in the role of the names of specific objects”.

Appeal to the texts of NCRL helps to identify texts of different genres and styles in which there are formations of zero suffixation, and organize the work of pleasure reading (reading with pleasure). Pleasure reading “is a method of teaching a foreign language, based on independent reading by students of authentic fiction in the target language. <...> A feature of this technique is the ability to focus on certain groups of lexical and grammatical phenomena necessary for enhancing students' speech skills” (Korneyeva, 2019). For example, when studying names of zero suffixation, you can refer to the novel by A.V. Ivanov's “Geographer drank the globe” (1995) (Ivanov, 2013), which describes the life of the provincial city of Perm in the mid-90s. 20th century and the search for its place in this life of the protagonist – a young geography teacher. In the novel, verbal, adjective, and sub-substantive formations are widely represented, including zero suffixation. First of all, these are names with meanings of an abstract action (*beseda*, *shum*, *krik*, *vizg*, over 60 examples in total), an abstract concept (*smysl*, *pravo*, *dobro*, *zlo*, about 40 examples), an abstract state (*toska*, *dosada*, *skuka*, 15 examples), places (*vykhod*, *vykhod*, *zasadah*, more than 30 examples), person (*paskuda*, *razzyava*, only 5 examples), a single act (*vystrel*, *vzvizg*, etc.), tools (*pila*, *grabli*, *prikklad*), with the value of an abstract attribute (*dal'*, *zelen'*, *tverd'*) and others. It is noteworthy that the key words of the novel are also the formation of zero suffixation: work, backwater and campaign. These words carry a special meaningful load and are peculiar tricks around which the main plot, compositional, emotional, figurative threads of the novel are concentrated. The names of zero suffixation in the work are actively used in describing the lessons of a novice teacher (*vopli*, *krik*, *shum*, etc.), in creating pictures of nature (*nasyp'*, *zakat*, *obryv*, etc.). Rich material for observation provides a study of the characteristics of the compatibility of these formations with each other, the features of constructing simple sentences with the names of zero suffixation, methods of alliteration, antitheses based on them and a significant number of adverbs, adverbial combinations and stable formations with the names of zero suffixation.

Thus, the use of NCRL in the study of zero-suffix formations allows one to solve many educational, methodological, didactic, linguistic and psychological problems, namely: to identify the features of the use of these formations in speech, to trace the differences in the semantics of word-building synonyms and the

peculiarity of their valence, to note the frequency of use of certain forms and on this basis to prepare a variety of didactic material to explain, consolidate the topic and control the knowledge gained.

Discussions

Studying the features of the functioning of zero derivational exhibitors in speech, we drew attention to the need to consider the artistic functions of this language phenomenon. The role of zero word-building exhibitors in texts of different genres and styles, namely: in proverbs, poetic works, in modern prose, raises questions. In scientific literature, the names of zero suffixation are often considered in connection with the study of occasional words in poetry at the beginning of the 20th century. However, the usual formations of this type also require special consideration. This is important both for research purposes and for the didactic support of the educational process.

Conclusion

The use of electronic and digital educational resources in the educational process in the age of rapid development of information technology is becoming an urgent requirement of the time. In modern conditions, the teacher is greatly assisted by educational and methodological complexes based on the principle of interactive interaction of subjects of the educational process. The task of the teacher is to help the student competently use the available information resources to form a high level of linguistic, linguistic and communicative competence and, in general, develop a linguistic personality that is close to the linguistic identity of a native speaker of the Russian language. In this regard, the importance of the National Corps of the Russian language (n.d.) as an information and reference system based on a collection of Russian texts in electronic form is growing. The work presents only one of the ways to use NCRL data in the educational process, examples are offered for removing lexical and syntactic difficulties on one, albeit a very complex topic. Meanwhile, in general, the didactic potential of NCRL has not yet been revealed and requires further study in the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language.

Acknowledgements

The work is performed according to the Russian Government Program of Competitive Growth of Kazan Federal University.

References

Antonova, V. E., Nakhabina, M. M., & Tolstykh, A. A. (2016). *Road to Russia: a textbook of the Russian language (first level)*. St. Petersburg: Zlatoust.

- Antonova, V. E., Nakhabina, M. M., & Tolstykh, A. A. (2017). *Road to Russia: a textbook of the Russian language (first level)*. St. Petersburg: Zlatoust.
- Efremova, T. F. (2000). *The new dictionary of the Russian language. Interpretative and derivational*. Moscow. Retrieved from <http://rus-yaz.niv.ru/doc/dictionary-efremova/index.htm>
- Egorova, A. F. (2016). *Difficult cases of Russian grammar: a collection of exercises on Russian as a foreign language*. St. Petersburg: Zlatoust.
- Ivanov, A. V. (2013). *The geographer drank the globe*. Retrieved from http://lib.ru/RUFANT/IWANOW_A/geograf_globus_propil.txt_with-big-pictures.html
- Korneyeva, T. A. (2016). On the Problem of Learning the Difficult Questions of Linguistics at Russian Lessons. *The European Proceedings of Social & Behavioural Sciences EpSBS, 12*, 313-321.
- Korneyeva, T. A. (2019). *Pleasure reading in teaching Russian grammar*. Word. Grammar. Speech: Materials of the VII International Scientific Conference "Text: Problems and Prospects. Aspects of learning to teach Russian as a foreign language". Moscow, Moscow State University; MAX Press. 213-214.
- Lopatin, V. V. (1966). Zero affixation in the system of Russian word formation. *Voprosy yazykoznaniya, 1*, 76-87.
- Markov, V. M. (2001). *Selected works in the Russian language*. Kazan: Publishing House DAS.
- Morkovkin, V. V., Bogacheva, G. F., & Lutskaya, N. M. (2016). *A large universal dictionary of the Russian language*. Moscow: Dictionaries of the XXI century.
- National corps of the Russian language. (n.d.). Retrieved from <http://www.ruscorpora.ru>
- Nikolaev, G. A. (2010). *Russian historical word formation: Theoretical problems*. Moscow: Librocom.
- Nikolaev, G. A. (2011). *Russian and Slavic word formation*. Kazan: Kazan University.
- Russian grammar: scientific papers. (2005). Retrieved from http://lukashevichus.info/knigi/russk_gramm_sl_shvedova_1.pdf

- Shansky, N. M. (1968). *Essays on Russian word formation*. Moscow: Publishing House Moscow University.
- Shaikhutdinova, R. I., Korneyeva, T. A., & Markova, T. D. (2016). The methods for studying zero affixation in school. *Modern Journal of Language Teaching Methods*, 76-80.
- Shaikhutdinova, R. I., Korneyeva, T. A., & Markova, T. D. (2017) Zero suffixation on synchrony and diachrony. *Astra Salvensis*, 5(10), 465-470.
- Volskaya, A. S., Korneyeva, T. A., & Markova, T. D. (2018). Word-formation, morphemic, etymological analysis in school. *Amazonia Investiga*, 7(15), 190-195.
- Zemskaya, E. A. (2013). *Modern Russian language. Word formation: textbook*. Moscow: Flinta Nauka.